

1 **An interleukin that functions in trastuzumab resistance.**

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6 Study of whole tumor gene expression in humans with pathological complete response (pCR) or
7 residual disease (RD) following treatment for HER2+ breast cancer revealed differential expression of the
8 interleukin IL-32 in patients with resistance to HER2-targeted treatment trastuzumab (Herceptin). IL-32
9 was expressed at relatively high levels in the tumors of humans displaying resistance to treatment with
10 trastuzumab as compared to those with pCR; the difference in IL-32 expression between those with
11 residual disease and pathological complete response was greater than the vast majority of the human
12 transcriptome. Studying whole transcription in human monocytes stimulated with IL-32 demonstrated
13 expression of this cytokine was associated with production of the chemokine CCL19. Accordingly, CCL19
14 was a major differentially expressed gene in the tumors of patients with trastuzumab resistance. We
15 suggest resistance to trastuzumab in humans with HER2+ breast cancer is associated with activation of
16 IL-32 leading to CCL19 production. Systems level analyses can provide important insights and inform
17 treatment decisions in human cancer.
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